

Impact of Job - Specific Stressors on Psychological Health of Police Personnel

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the prevalent issue of job stressors among police personnel and its significant impacts on their psychological health and overall well-being. It highlights the critical nature of the profession and the inherent stressors involved, to achieve better organizational and mental health outcomes. Since police personnel are subjected to high levels of stress on everyday basis, it is important their stressors are handled efficiently. The aim of the present study was to determine the various job-related stressors which negatively influence the performance and wellbeing of the police personnel. A sample of 45 police personnel was collected from Jammu district through cluster sampling. The police personnel ages ranged between 20 to 60 years. The statistical tools used in this study were independent sample t-test, one way ANOVA and regression analysis. The results revealed that police stressors significantly impact psychological health (social dysfunction, anxiety and depression, and loss of confidence). Implications of the study for the police personnel are discussed. Based on these results various recommendations have thus been suggested in the paper.

Keywords: Stressors, psychological health, wellbeing, strain, anxiety

INTRODUCTION

A police personnel job is more stressful in comparison with other occupations (Goodman, 1990). With the advent of globalization, the opportunities of coming together for committing organized crimes have increased, along with international implications of crimes involving drugs, trafficking, intellectual frauds and cyber-crimes like phishing. The term “stress” was coined by Hans Selye in 1936, who defined it as “the non-specific response of the body to any demand for change”. Stress is defined as a state of mental and emotional pressure or strain, caused by challenging or unfavorable circumstances. It is an outside force that rules an individual’s feelings and behavior. The National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health (1999) defines stress as ‘The harmful physical and

emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, needs of the worker’. However, it has been strongly argued that the job performance of a police officer is affected when they undergo chronic stress. (McGreedy,1974). “Police stress” refers to the negative pressure related to police work. Whereas, stressor is a particular circumstance, requirement, or situation that can induce stress, a biochemical change in behavioral, physiological, and/or psychological health. Since police personnel’s are subjected to high levels of stress on everyday basis, it is important their stressors are handled efficiently. Therefore, it is important for them to use positive coping strategies and focus on improving their overall wellbeing.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Author/Year	Variable studied	Objectives	Research Methodology	Findings
Bano (2011)	Job stress	To identify causes of stress and also empirically investigate the socio-demographic factors	Aligarh (Uttar Pradesh); 65 female police personnel; judgmental	Existing body of knowledge and contribute to the understanding of causes of stress and role of socio-demographic factors

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		affecting stress level among police personnel	sampling technique	in affecting stress level among police personnel
Naik et al. (2012)	Personality and stress coping strategies	To study the association of personality traits and methods for coping with psychological stress in police personnel	Goa; 100 constables and head constables; Convenience sampling technique	There is an association between personality traits and the level of psychological distress
Shacklock et al. (2012)	Emotional intelligence, job satisfaction, well-being and engagement in policing	To examine the effect of emotional intelligence upon the job satisfaction, well-being and engagement of police officers	Australia; 193 police officers; survey method	Police officers affective commitment mediates the negative relationship between their engagement at work and their turnover intentions
Chitra (2014)	Occupational Stress	To understand and analyze the specific stressors experienced by the police personnel of different ranks	Mumbai; 500 police personnel; stratified random sampling technique	Police personnel having duration of service up to 15 years experience slightly more amount of stress
Maria et al. (2018)	Physical health, burnout, depression and well-being	To examine the relationship between work efforts and burnout among police officers	Germany; 1787 members; survey method	Health-oriented leadership had a negatively affect related to levels of burnout, depression, and physical complaints among police officers and is positively related to their state of well-being
Park and Cho (2021)	Physical and mental health symptoms	To compare the stress levels and physical and mental health symptoms of patrol officers and emergency dispatch officers	South Korea; 254 patrol officers and 177 emergency dispatch officers; random sampling technique	Stress related to organizational management had the highest impact on physical and mental health, and differences in the stressors affecting the two group's physical and mental health were found

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this study are:

1. To study the perception of respondents related to police stressors and mental health based on their gender, marital status, age and educational qualification.
2. To study the impact of police stressors on mental health (social dysfunction, anxiety and depression and loss of confidence).

3. To frame strategies to reduce stress among police personnel and improve psychological health of police personnel.

HYPOTHESES

The various hypotheses formulated are as follows:

H1: There is a significant difference in the perception of respondents related to police stressors and mental health due to their marital status.

H2: There is a significant difference in the perception of respondents related to police stressors and mental health due to their gender.

H3: There is a significant difference in the perception of respondents related to police stressors and mental health due to their age.

H4: There is a significant difference in the perception of respondents related to police stressors and mental health due to their educational qualification.

H5: Police stress significantly impacts the mental health of police personnel (social dysfunction, anxiety and depression and loss of confidence).

Sample

- **Sample Area:** The area covered for collecting information regarding the study was Jammu Division.
- **Sample Size:** The sample size was of 45 police personnel.
- **Sampling Technique:** The sampling technique used in this study was cluster sampling.

Statistical Tools

The statistical tools used in this study were independent sample t-test, one-way ANOVA and regression analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

METHOD

Table 1: Marital Status-wise t-test results for Police Stressors and Mental Health

Construct	Marital Status	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Sig.(p)
Police stressors	Married	2.92	0.24	0.12	0.79
	Unmarried	2.92	0.22		
Social dysfunction	Married	1.67	0.39	1.09	0.09
	Unmarried	1.53	0.24		
Anxiety and depression	Married	2.40	0.59	-0.14	0.15
	Unmarried	2.43	0.39		
Loss of confidence	Married	1.47	0.53	0.79	0.75
	Unmarried	1.31	0.60		

Table 2: Gender-wise t-test results for Police Stressors and Mental Health

Construct	Gender	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Sig.(p)
Police stressors	Male	2.92	0.24	0.12	0.79
	Female	2.91	0.22		
Social dysfunction	Male	1.67	0.39	1.09	0.09
	Female	1.53	0.24		
Anxiety and depression	Male	2.40	0.59	-0.14	0.15
	Female	2.43	0.39		
Loss of confidence	Male	1.47	0.53	0.79	0.75
	Female	1.32	0.60		

Table 3: Age wise ANOVA results for Police Stressors and Mental Health

Construct	20-30 years		30-40 years		40-50 years		50-60 years		ANOVA	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	F	Sig.(p)
Police stressors	2.83	0.19	2.89	0.38	2.96	0.19	2.99	0.22	1.15	0.34
Social dysfunction	1.65	0.34	1.61	0.47	1.64	0.37	1.59	0.35	0.06	0.98
Anxiety and depression	2.36	0.59	2.41	0.58	2.50	0.59	2.30	0.46	0.27	0.85
Loss of confidence	1.27	0.33	1.67	0.93	1.47	0.57	1.44	0.46	0.76	0.52

Table 4: Educational qualification-wise ANOVA results for Police Stressors and Mental Health

Construct	High School		Intermediate		Graduate		ANOVA	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	F	Sig. (p)
Police stressors	2.90	0.14	3.03	0.21	2.84	0.25	3.41	0.43
Social dysfunction	1.62	0.26	1.54	0.30	1.71	0.43	0.95	0.39
Anxiety and depression	2.47	0.60	2.26	0.40	2.50	0.63	0.87	0.43
Loss of confidence	1.37	0.44	1.50	0.52	1.40	0.62	0.18	0.83

Table 5: Regression analysis of Police stressors on Social Dysfunction

Predictors	B	Beta (β)	Sig.	R	R ²
Constant	3.31	-	0.00	0.37	0.14
Police stressors	-0.57	-0.37	0.013		

Table 6: Regression analysis of Police Stressors on Anxiety and Depression

Predictors	B	Beta (β)	Sig.	R	R ²
Constant	5.40	-	0.00	0.43	0.18
Police stressors	-1.02	0.43	0.003		

Table 7: Regression analysis of Police Stressors on Loss of Confidence

Predictors	B	Beta (β)	Sig.	R	R ²
Constant	4.72	-	0.00	0.47	0.22
Police Stressors	-1.12	-0.47	0.001		

Therefore, social workers, psychologists, personnel psychologists and other mental health professional should develop and focus on intervention strategies for improving the psychological health and mental wellbeing of the police personnel. The implications also present a platform upon which organizational commitment of the police personnel could be understood and managed. Sequel to the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The findings disclose that male police personnel are more in number as compared to the females in the police department. There is usually a misconception in the minds of the people that police job suits only males. But females can also perform this job effectively if they are properly encouraged. Therefore, the study suggests that Jammu and Kashmir Police department should also implement national level special schemes for women police personnel such as Mahila Police Volunteers scheme, Police Mitra Scheme, Samudayak Police Yojna, etc. for encouraging more female aspirants to join the department.
2. The findings reveal that there is no significant effect on the perception of respondents related to

police stressors and mental health based on their marital status. Though both married and unmarried personnel think alike about police stressors and mental health, however, the police department should implement supportive programs for married personnel such as flexible work schedules, job sharing, compressed work weeks, etc.

3. As there is no significant effect on the perception of respondents related to police stressors and mental health based on their age. This means that personnel of different age groups have similar thinking regarding police stressors and mental health. Therefore, the department should implement similar strategies such as organize employee counseling sessions, stress. reduction programs, supportive work environment, etc. for all age groups but assign more strenuous tasks to younger personnel.
4. Since police stressors significantly impact mental health, it is suggested that department should implement stress management programs, assign psychologists, support the families of personnel, ensure work life balance etc.

5. Department should implement national level special schemes like Bhadratha and Arogya Bhadratha scheme, along with other schemes being implemented by the department for the welfare of police families.

CONCLUSION

Police personnel suffering from work stress experiences physical syndrome and psychological problems which in turn affects their psychological wellbeing. Stress in law enforcement is difficult to measure and cannot be attributed to just one factor. In essence, police stress is a complex formula that has many different contributory factors. Most of the stressors are categorized into intra-personal, inter personal, work-related, family and if stress is neglected it effects on their mental and physical health and their family relations also adversely affected. The positive attitude and meditation will be helpful for coping the stress. Thinking in a broader perspective of life will change stress. There are many ways for managing stress, such as meditation, yoga, etc. The negative stress or distress kills the employee's positive attitude and it turns to absent, turnover, immoral, anxiety, depression, aggressive and so on. Hence, it will be successful if it makes distress into eu-stress the healthy lifestyle as well as organizational well-being will be changed.

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